

**THE EFFECT OF QAT CHEWING ON
ELECTROCARDIOGRAPHIC TRACING IN
HEALTHY MALE INDIVIDUALS**

A THESIS

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BY

BELQUISE ABDULLAH AL-TAHAMI

DEPARTMENT OF PHARMACOLOGY & THERAPEUTICS

FACULTY OF MEDICINE AND HEALTH SCIENCES

A UNIVERSITY SANA

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UNDER THE SUPERVISION OF

Dr Nageeb Abdul-Galil Mohammed Hassan
Professor in Clinical Pharmacology
Department of Pharmacology and Therapeutics
Faculty of Medicine and Health Science
Sana'a University

Dr Salah I. Mosfer
Assistant Professor in Pharmacology Department
of Pharmacology and Therapeutics
Faculty of Medicine and Health Science
Sana'a University

Summary

Qat chewing is a widespread habit among Yemeni and African population and spread to west by immigrants. Qat is consumed due to its stimulant effect that results from its cathinone contents. The effects of Qat chewing on different body systems have been studied extensively, however its effect in ECG has not been studied.

This study aims to determine if there is any ECG change among Qat chewers (regular ≥ 5 days per week, rare $\leq$ once weekly) in comparison to those non-Qat chewers, To determine if there is any difference between ECG changes among regular and rare Qat chewers, To determine if there is QTc dispersion among Qat chewers (regular and rare) in comparison to non-Qat chewers and to measure arterial blood pressure (systolic and diastolic, mean arterial blood pressure and pulse pressure) and heart rate as assessment parameters.

The study designed prospectively and 90 adult healthy male subjects, were randomly selected from Qat chewing sessions age ranged from 18-40 years old with body mass index (BMI) ranged from 17 to 30 and they divided into three groups according to Qat chewing frequency {regular ≥ 5 days per week and chew Qat for more than 3 years, rare $\leq$ once weekly, and non chewer as control}. The study was taken place at health center in Sana'a, Yemen. Qat obtained from local market, of Dula typed that contain cathinone in certain known concentration and of certain amount. The chewing time was about 4 hours then spilt out the leaves. ECG recording was done at Zero time (1 hour before Qat chewing), 1 hour, 2 hours and 3 hours during Qat chewing, 1 hour after spitting out the leaves, 18 hours and 24 hours from starting chewing Qat. Auto heart rate, P-wave, PR interval, QRS complex, ST segment, QT interval and T-waves were automatically interpreted by the ECG machine. QTc dispersion was calculated using the difference between the maximum and the minimum QTc in ECG leads. QTc dispersion ≥ 60 ms was consider abnormally increased. Blood pressure (systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) blood pressure) and manual heart rate (mHR) were measured at Zero time (1 hour before Qat chewing), 1 hour, 2 hours and 3 hours during Qat chewing, 1 hour

after spitting out the leaves, 18 hours and 24 hours from starting chewing Qat. The blood pressure measured using a mercury based cuff sphygmomanometer on the bared arm in the setting position and the heart rate measured manually using the radial pulse in the setting position. The mean arterial blood pressure (MABP) was also calculated as it = systolic + diastolic over 3 and the pulse pressure (PP) = systolic blood pressure – diastolic blood pressure. Statistical analysis of data was performed with a personal computer using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

The most important results obtained from this study were that a significant and progressive increased heart rate and decreased PR interval, QRS complex and QT interval at hourly interval during chewing Qat compared with baseline (zero time) reach the peak at 3 hrs and it started to return 1 h after ceasing to chew Qat for regular and rare Qat chewers ($P < 0.05$), a significant and progressive increased in QTc dispersion at hourly interval during chewing Qat compared with baseline (zero time), reached the peak at 3 hrs and started to decrease 1 h after ceasing chewing Qat for regular and rare Qat chewers and the increased over the time was more pronounced in regular Qat chewers. However, it did not exceed 60 ms at any measured time. For non-Qat chewers no

changes occur. Also a significant and progressive increased in systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, main arterial blood pressure and manual heart rate at hourly interval during chewing Qat compared with baseline (zero time), reach the peak at 3 hrs and started to decline 1 h after ceasing to chew Qat for regular and rare Qat chewers ($P < 0.05$).

In conclusion Qat chewing considered as a risk factor for ischemic heart diseases in predisposed individuals as it affects QTc dispersion value and this may be an indicator of change in coronary blood vessels in addition to the increased in blood pressure and heart rate that increased cardiac demand and provoke myocardial ischemia. Therefore, individuals with heart diseases should be avoided chewing Qat leaves.